

Development of an experimental setup to investigate the lunar water cycle in the VOLARIS project.

J. N. Brecher (j.n.brecher@tum.de)¹, M. Amorós-Trepat¹, A. Peschel¹ and P. Reiss¹. ¹Technical University of Munich, Ottobrunn, Germany

Introduction: The study of volatiles in the solar system might provide valuable clues about its formation and evolution. Airless solar system bodies offer an ideal environment for investigating exogenous volatile elements because they can interact directly with the planetary surface, with space weathering processes being preserved over geological timescales [1]. The Moon, due to its accessibility from Earth and the relatively abundant data, is one of the preferred bodies for the investigation of volatiles [2, 3], and insights from the Moon are transferable to other bodies with surface-bounded exospheres [4].

Since remote sensing missions revealed surficial water near the lunar poles and in permanently shadowed regions, the interest in lunar water for future missions and in-situ resource utilisation has grown [5]. However, there is no ground truth for lunar water yet, and open questions remain about the origin of the water and other volatiles, as well as their concentrations at different locations on the Moon [6]. Over the last decades, several hypotheses and numerical models have been established, and different source and loss mechanisms, such as micrometeoroid impacts and thermal migration, have been identified as contributors to the lunar water cycle [6]. However, experimental investigations mainly focus on individual processes within single domains, e.g., simulating micrometeoroid impacts on samples at nm- to mm-scale [7, 8] and diffusion processes at scales up to cm-scale [9].

Thermal migration and diffusion of water molecules into and through the lunar regolith depend on temperature and concentration gradients, as well as physical soil properties. Diurnal and seasonal variations in temperature enable so-called thermal pumping. Over time, water molecules migrate into deeper layers, leading to a peak in water concentration in the upper half meter [10, 11]. However, according to [10], only a few per cent of the water delivered to the surface diffuses into the subsurface. Water that remains at the surface can migrate laterally by ballistic hops or can be released by micrometeoroid impacts [12].

The project VOLARIS, funded by the European Research Council, aims to improve our understanding of the lunar water cycle by combining laboratory experiments with numerical simulations at local to global scales and across domains (subsurface, surface, and exosphere). One of the main goals is to investigate the underlying hypothesis that more near-surface lunar water reservoirs exist than are currently estimated [13].

Methodology: To research the combined interaction of source and loss mechanisms of the lunar water cycle, we will build a thermal-vacuum chamber that creates a relevant environment with temperatures down to ~ 100 K and a pressure of $\sim 10^{-6}$ mbar. To investigate the migration of water into and through a lunar regolith simulant sample and its subsequent release by simulated micrometeoroid impacts, several experiments are planned. An initially dry sample will be exposed to a residual water atmosphere to simulate the delivery of water molecules to the surface. A heater placed above the sample's surface will expose the sample to shortened lunar diurnal temperature cycles on a hours-to-days timescale, establishing a representative temperature gradient within the sample that drives diffusion. In subsequent experiments, sample parameters, e.g., the initial water concentration, the supply of water to the surface via a residual water atmosphere, and the properties of the heating cycle, will be varied to determine their influence on the process.

The temperature inside the sample will be monitored with several PT1000 sensors placed at different heights and lateral positions. Additionally, the sample surface temperature will be measured with an IR camera mounted perpendicular to the surface. Furthermore, the feasibility of dielectric spectroscopy measurements and their subsequent inversion for spatial and temporal resolution of water concentration within the sample is being investigated. Similar measurement techniques, such as those employed for the PROSPECT mission [14], have already been successfully applied to determine the water content of regolith via electric permittivity.

In another experimental scenario, a thermally cycled, wet regolith sample will be irradiated with a short-pulsed laser to observe the effects of a simulated micrometeoroid impact. Released volatiles will be monitored by a mass spectrometer, and water migration processes triggered by the impact will be investigated.

Results: A preliminary experimental setup was built to investigate temperature profiles within a bed of lunar regolith, perform feasibility studies on thermal cycling, and measure the sample's dielectric properties to infer its water content. The current sample, made from JSC-1A, with a diameter of 15 cm, a height of 10 cm and a porosity of 30%, was placed underneath a heating coil in a thermal-vacuum chamber at a pressure of $\sim 10^{-2}$ mbar. The sample holder was mounted on a temperature-controlled plate. In the sample, PT1000 sensors were mounted on strings at various heights and lateral positions. Figure 1 shows

the experimental setup inside the thermal vacuum chamber. The heater was placed inside a heat shield, 65 mm above the sample surface.

Until now, sinusoidal temperature cycles with periods up to 8 hours have been performed in a room-temperature vacuum environment, resulting in a temperature of ~ 325 K at the sample surface. An increase of more than 3 K over the duration of the experiment is visible in the upper ~ 30 mm, while temperature oscillations following the cyclic heating are measured only in the upper ~ 15 mm, demonstrating the feasibility of inducing a thermal cycle in a regolith bed via infrared radiation from a heater above. A COMSOL simulation of the setup is being correlated with the measurement data to further investigate the sample's thermal properties and assess thermal losses to its environment.

Future Work: Further testing with the preliminary experimental setup is planned, including experiments in a cooled environment with cold plate temperatures down to ~ 200 K. The COMSOL model of the setup will be further correlated to complement the experimental investigations and extrapolate to longer timescales. Also, icy samples and various surface features, such as cm-scale rocks, will be investigated. To quantify subsurface ice concentration, the inversion algorithm for electric permittivity measurements will be applied to real measurement data, and different electrode configurations will be examined. The results gained from these initial tests will inform the design of a new thermal-vacuum system dedicated to the full-scale experiments of VOLARIS, targeted to start in early 2027.

Acknowledgements: This project has been funded by The European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme – grant agreement number 101164002. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the ERC. Neither the European Union nor the granting authorities can be held responsible for them.

Figure 1: Preliminary experimental setup placed inside a thermal vacuum chamber.

References: [1] Hodges, R. et al. (1973) *LPSC Proceedings* 4, 2855. [2] Lucey, P. G. et al. (2022) *Geochemistry* 82, 3. [3] Hurley et al. (2023) *Reviews in Mineralogy and Geochemistry* 89 (1), 787–827. [4] Steckloff, J. K. et al. (2022) *Icarus* 384, 115092. [5] National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine. (2023) *The National Academies Press*. [6] Reiss, P. (2024) *PNAS*. [7] Zhu, C. et al. (2019) *PNAS*. [8] Weber, I. et al. (2020) *Earth and Planetary Science Letters* 530, 115884. [9] Li, Y. et al. (2025) *The Planetary Science Journal* 6.8, 196. [10] Schorghofer, N. et al. (2014) *The Astrophysical Journal* 788.2, 169. [11] Reiss, P. et al. (2021) *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets* 126.5, e2020JE006742. [12] Smolka, A. (2023) *Icarus* 397, 15508. [13] Reiss, P. et al. (2025) *The Project Repository Journal*, 24(1), 86–89. [14] Gscheidle, C. and Reiss, P. (2024) *EPSC2024-559*. [15] Schorghofer, N. et al. (2024) *The Planetary Science Journal* 5, 120.